

Behavioral Problems in Children of Different Age Group Due to Lockdown

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To determine the behavioral changes among the students attending online class of age 6 to 18 years.

Method: A cross-sectional survey of 109 pupils in the age range of 6 to 18 years was conducted. The ASEB Child Behavior Checklist and Youth Self-Report were the scales utilized in this study. Parents of students between the ages of 6 and 10 filled out the CBCL form, and students between the ages of 11 and 18 filled out the YSR form.

Result: After dividing the sample into the age groups of 6 to 10 and 11 to 12 years, the results indicate a significant difference with a p value of 0.049. The age group of 6 to 10 years had an analytical score that was noticeably lower in terms of behavioral changes (normal: 42.9%, borderline: 55.6%, clinical: 20.0%) than the age group of 11 to 18 years (normal: 57.1%, borderline: 44.4%, clinical: 80.0%).

Conclusion: According to this study's findings, students who take online classes exhibit mild behavioral changes before or during the pandemic, and switching from classroom-based to online learning can be very stressful for kids because it deviates from their usual routine and they are not used to the new style of learning. The anxiousness that students may be experiencing should also be acknowledged by parents and teachers.

KEYWORDS: Online class, Students, Behaviour

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INTRODUCTION

In India the spread of virus lead to a complete national lockdown and due to the increase, the lockdown was extended and the schools and other institutes remained closed. To overcome this crisis the government and private sectors opted to the work and study from home through online sources. Online class mode of education is new normal for school going students. Some students were excited about this as they could continue their education even during the pandemic. But for some it became a challenge attending these classes. According to a parent of an 8-year-old attending online classes complaint that the school shouldn't be kept online for small kids, since their concentration span is less and won't pay attention much. The students also stated that they don't like the online class (Prashanthi Karyala & Sarita Kamat 2020)¹. The online classes mainly focus on the academic completion of the students. Where the classes are conducted using the video conferencing meeting applications and other virtual platforms. This prevents students' participation in school activities that help them to improve their skills. Which promotes the physical, emotional and social well-being of the students.

STUDENTS

The students' routines are affected as the school remains closed and are facing challenging situations due to pandemic in India. In children and adolescents aged students the school plays an important role for their development. The physical class room with presence of teachers and other peers will promote the learning more interesting and enjoyable as there is a face-to-face interaction among students and teachers. In a survey conducted by UNESCO in the month of April 2020, reported that more than 188 countries closed their schools due to the covid-19 pandemic. It also showed that about 1.5 million students are affected. Audrey Azoulay, Director general of UNESCO commented that "the global scale and speed of the current educational disruption is unparalleled". (Lee, Joyce 2020)²

BEHAVIOUR AND EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS

The behavior and emotional problems are more found now days in children and adolescents as they have to adopt to the changes occurred due the current pandemic. The studies

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shows that they were more prone to symptoms of clinginess, irritability, anxiety, sadness and feeling of loneliness and other emotional distress. (Wen Yan Jiao et al 2020)³. According to the parents, the children face different problems such as isolation, disturbed sleep, nightmares, poor appetite, agitation, inattention as they are away from their school and friends in covid-19 pandemic. A systemic approach towards the children can help them overcome these psychological distresses. (Shweta Singh 2020)⁴.

Need for the study

The Covid-19 pandemic resulted a lot of challenges to the people than they have faced it before. Especially, Children and adolescents who are affected as their schools remained closed. And being at home restricted from all their usual activities can have an impact on their mental health.

In India 320 million students are affected due to the closure of schools. And amidst of all these the students attend their online education. Studies were conducted among the students and parents of different countries about the impact caused due to online learning in the time of covid-19 pandemic (Sabina Yeasmina et.al 2020)⁵. Parents stated that though online class could help the children to study but it also caused a poor self-regulation and short attention span. And were worried about its effect on the children's development (Chuanmei Donga et al 2020)⁶. The situation in India is also the same as the pandemic due to corona virus is continuing. The current situation can affect students in many ways, mainly the psychological distress which can result into behavioral and emotional problems (Shweta Singh et al 2020)⁴. A healthy mind and body are very essential when it comes to the growing young students and helping them in early stage can improve their development in a good manner. Henceforth, this study has to be conducted for an early screening of behavior and emotional problems in children's and adolescent who are attending online class in the pandemic.

Aim of the study

To determine the behavioral changes among the students attending online class of age 6 to 18 years.

Objectives of the study

To determine change of behavior and emotional problems in students attending online classes.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The goal of the case study was to collect comprehensive data.

Sample

One hundred and nine students attending online classes in Chennai and parts of Kerala were involved in this study. The

samples were selected through convenience sampling.

Instrument used

The child behavior checklist (CBCL) was developed by M. Thomas Achenbach (1960). There are other forms under this such as the Youth self - report (YSR), Teachers self- report (TRF). The CBCL is screening tool used to measure emotional and behavioral problems. The CBCL is used in age group 6 to 18 years. And YSR is self-report used in age group 11 to 18 years. The questions are similar in both, there are 113 questions and it's scored on a three-point Likert scale. Where, (0: Absent 1: Occur sometimes 2: Occurs often)⁷.

Data analysis

The participants were selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. The purpose of the study was well explained to students and their parents and electronic informed consent was obtained. The questionnaire was sent through google forms and the filled forms were taken for data analysis.

RESULTS

The male participants were 46.79% and female were 53.21%. Students age group between 6 to 18 years have M=13.15 with 4.15 standard deviation. The frequency of age 6 to 10 years is 41 and the percentage is 37.61%. The frequency of age group 11 to 18 years is 68 and percentage 62.39%. The ASEBA scores distribution for normal is 64.22%, borderline is 8.26% and clinical is 27.2% (TABLE 1).

The ANOVA was used to compare the ASEBA interpretation based on the scoring done in students attending online classes. The maximum and minimum of ASEBA score was categorized based on the 'range of scoring' that is for normal range, the minimum score is 10 and maximum is 65, borderline range, minimum score 66 and maximum 70 and clinical range minimum score 74 and maximum 112. The p value is highly significant as it is less than 0.01 i.e., the p value found to be 0.000. Hence there is a high significance on the ASEBA interpretation (TABLE 2). The association between gender and age regarding ASEBA score, which was done using chi-square test. where the p value for gender wise category is 0.911. And the p value for age wise category is 0.049 (TABLE 3).

Table 1 shows the number of students participated in the age group 6 to 10 years and 11 to 18 years and the total number of female and male students. Where, the normal (70), borderline (9) and clinical range (30) students were determined based on ASEBA interpretation. Thus, showing presence of behavioral changes and emotional issues among students.

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Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Variables

Demographic Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Age	6 - 10 Years	41	37.61
	11 - 18 Years	68	62.39
	Mean \pm SD	13.15 \pm 4.156	
Gender	Male	51	46.79
	Female	58	53.21
ASEBA	Normal	70	64.22
	Border Line	9	8.26
	Clinical	30	27.52

Table 2 analyses the ASEBA interpretation based on CBCL & YSR scoring that total number of students and their categorized into normal, borderline and clinical range. The p value obtained is 0.000 and f value is 128.865. It is a significance score.

Table 2: ASEBA interpretation based on CBCL & YSR scoring range among students

ASEBA Score	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max	F-Value (P-Value)
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Normal	70	39.84	16.402	35.93	43.75	10	65	128.865 (0.000) S
Border Line	9	68.00	1.732	66.67	69.33	66	70	
Clinical	30	89.47	10.634	85.50	93.44	74	112	
Total	109	55.83	26.358	50.82	60.83	10	112	

S – Significance NS – Not Significance

Table 3 gives the gender and age wise association regarding ASEBA score, where the gender male total percentage is 46.8% and the female total percentage is 53.2%. The chi square value is 0.311 with p value 0.911, which is not significant. The age wise association within two age group categories are, 6 -10 years total percentage is 37.6% and 11 to 18 years total percentage is 62.4%. The chi square value is 6.150 with p value is 0.049, which is a significant score. According to a study conducted the distribution of behavior and emotional problems was 14.7% (borderline is 5.2% and clinical is 9.5%). In the total problems, the females are 16.0% and males 13.2%.

Table 3: Gender and Age association based on ASEBA score

		ASEBA Score					χ^2 - Value	P - Value	
		Normal	Border Line	Clinical	Total				
GENDER	Male	N 34 % 48.6%	4 44.4%	13 43.3%	51 46.8%	0.311	0.911 NS		
	Female	N 36 % 51.4%	5 55.6%	17 56.7%	58 53.2%				
Age	6 - 10 Years	N 30 % 42.9%	5 55.6%	6 20.0%	41 37.6%			6.150	0.049 S
	11 - 18 Years	N 40 % 57.1%	4 44.4%	24 80.0%	68 62.4%				

CONCLUSION

This study elaborates the significant difference in the behavioral and emotional problems in students attending online class during the pandemic 2020. Based on the ASEBA interpretation there is significant difference in the behavior students when compared age wise categories and there is no

significant difference compared to gender wise categories. The overall percentage score i.e., normal is 64.22%, borderline is 8.26% and clinical is 27.52%. This study concludes that students attending online classes are facing marginal behavior and emotional issues.

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DISCUSSION

The study was conducted among students attending online classes. To determine the behavioral changes among students of age group 6 to 18 years (Masare et al 2019)⁸. The students report collected and interpreted according to the ASEBA score, where it has three ranges categorized as normal, borderline, clinical. The study was conducted for early screening of behavior problems in students who are attending online classes during the pandemic. Within a certain class, students undertake complex behaviors in allotting time between different tools and activities (Rosalina Rebucas)⁹. There are countless distractions while learning at home. According to a nationally representative **Education Week Research Center survey** of more than 900 educators, more than a fifth said that during school-building closures, they have taught live, virtual classes at specific, predesignated times where students can interact with each other and with the teacher. That can give students a sense of normalcy and connection—but it can also leave teachers trying to keep students on task and engaged in virtual environments they are not familiar with. As a consequence, expectations for student behavior in online classes range widely from strict adherence to physical classroom rules to much more laissez-faire approaches during the school building shutdowns. And the lack of those informal supports, as well as other factors, could be having an impact on the level of attention students are giving to their online schoolwork. The Education Week Research Center survey found that when teachers were asked to select a major challenge for instruction during school closures, a third of teachers said their students have “a lot more trouble focusing on work at home than they do at school (Madeline Will 2020)¹⁰.”

RECOMMENDATIONS

Study should be conducted in large group and parents; teachers and health professionals should promote students' good mental health during the pandemic. The integration of online counselling and stress management program would help mitigate the stress of the students during distance learning.

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